

Characterization of bycatch organisms from the trawl boats operated along the Kerala coast

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Key Points:

- One of the main threats to the world's oceans is bycatch, which is the accidental capture of unused or unmanaged species.
- According to this study, in April 2015, 597 bycatch organisms were found in the Neendakara fishing harbor.
- Research on bycatch species is crucial to comprehending the challenges and addressing the bycatch-related problems.

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Abstract

Bycatch refers to “discarded catch of marine species and unobserved mortality due to a direct encounter with fishing vessels and gear”. It negatively affects the marine ecosystems and sustainable management of fisheries resources. The present study is based on the data collected from the Neendakara fishing harbour along the southwest coast of India. The samples were collected in April 2015 from commercial boats operating bottom trawl nets with a cod-end mesh size of 35mm. A total of 597 bycatch organisms were encountered from the sampling station (Crab: 9 species belong to 5 families, Fishes: 17 species belonging to 16 families, Stomatopoda: 1 species belonging to 1 family, and Mollusca: 14 species belonging to 13 families). Length and weight were measured for some fishes, molluscans, crustaceans and stomatopods captured as bycatch along the Neendakara coast, Kollam, Indian Ocean. The possibility of survival for discarded animals is a significant topic; large species of finfish and crustaceans, as well as mature individuals, have high survival rates, but juveniles and small finfish species have low survival rates. Characterization of bycatch fish and shellfish from the trawl boats based on their type and size is very important for understanding the problems related to bycatch and taking necessary actions to mitigate the problems.

Keywords: Bycatch organisms, fishes, discards, trawls.

1. Introduction

Bycatch refers to “discarded catch of marine species and unobserved mortality due to a direct encounter with fishing vessels and gear”, these unintentionally caught animals often suffer injuries or die. It is an issue both ecologically and economically. Bycatch of non-target fish species can contribute to overfishing and slow efforts to rebuild fish stocks, also have negative economic and social impacts on fishermen and their communities. Consequently, the large bycatch of a non-target species may lead a fishery to close early. Bycatch has an ecological impact on fisheries production and marine ecosystems by altering the availability of prey. In the case of protected species, bycatch can negatively affect species like dolphins, sea turtles, protected

fish (e.g. Chum Salmon *Oncorhynchus keta*) and whales by harming animals, eventually leading to population declines, and impeding population recovery. Other consequences on marine mammals may include the removal of their preferred prey and sometimes habitat damage (*NOAA Fisheries Website 2022*).

India is a country blessed with a long coastline (approximately 7500km) which supports a wide variety of fish and other organisms. The Indian marine fisheries is a rapidly expanding industry with enormous growth potential and a major contributor to foreign exchange earnings. Kelleher (2005) reported that the average annual global discard has been re-estimated to be 7.3 million tonnes. Global capture fishery production has been plateauing and has more or less

stabilized at around 80 million tonnes (FAO, 2014). The biology, population characteristics, and length-weight relationships (LWRs) of all fish species (target, discard, and bycatch) in the world’s seas and oceans must be thoroughly studied. The maximum weight and length are essential parameters in fishery science and life history studies. These measurements are applied directly or indirectly in most stock assessment models (Cengiz et al., 2019). Statistical data of Indian fisheries is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Statistical data of Indian fisheries (Fish production in 2021 - 2022).

Fishing down effect is pervasive in world fisheries, including Indian fisheries (Bhathal, 2005; Pauly et al., 2003; Vivekanandhan et al., 2005). Marine fish production in India which was only 15.55 lakh tonnes in 1980-81, increased to 41.27 lakh tonnes in 2021-2022 (*Handbook Fisheries Statistics 19.01.2022 (Final File).cdr (dof.gov.in) 2022*). A study has reported that the average discards of mechanised trawlers in Kerala were 429,074 t during 2008 (Pramod, 2010). The highest levels of bycatch occurred in shrimp trawlers. There are several categories of bycatch obtained from shrimp trawlers such as a) Bycatch of no

commercial value which includes species of coelenterates, echinoderms, several species of gastropods, crustaceans etc. b) Seasonal bycatch which includes species that of commercial importance in a certain season if caught in large quantities, but in small proportion is of little commercial value and is usually dumped overboard and c) area-specific bycatch: where in the bycatch of one area may not necessarily be the bycatch of another includes (Lobo, 2007). Boopendranath (2010) reported that bycatch quantity varies according to season, area of the fishing operation, type of fishery and type of fishing gears. Around the world, the fishing industry has developed several bycatch reduction systems to reduce the impact of fishing on non-target resources. Van Beek (1998) reported that in common non-commercial species in the by-catch are being discarded back into the sea. However, any form of fish protein became a major raw material for feed and fertilizer production. Most of the low-value bycatch (LVB) brought to the shore are kept without much preservation and utilized widely to feed livestock/fish, either directly or as fish meal/oil (Simon et al., 2005). LVB landings not only contain non-profitable fishes but also juveniles of several commercially important fishes of below minimum landing size (MLS) / less profitable owing to market conditions (Catchpole et al., 2005; Stobutzki et al., 2001). Removing significant proportions of any species risks upsetting their balance in marine ecosystems. Thus, monitoring of data related to bycatch organisms is necessary for mitigating problems. The present study aims to understand the biodiversity of bycatch organisms at Neendakara harbour.

2. Materials and Methods

Data on bycatch and discard were collected from selected commercial trawlers operated from Kollam, Neendakara (Figure 2: Latitude - 8°56'18.32" N, Longitude - 76°32'33.78" E), during the monsoon season. The landing centre is situated at the mouth of the Ashtamudi backwaters. Data collection was done twice a week. The unsorted portion of the catch, which is normally discarded by fishermen, was collected and labelled. Sex was determined by examining the gonads of samples. Trawl fishery data from major trawl landing centres were estimated to get the bycatch and catch scenario in trawl fisheries, trawl catch from major fishing harbours of India.

Figure 2: Sampling station - Neendakara Harbour, Kerala, India.

The landing has been classified as two, **1**) those landed for “edible uses” and **2**) landed as low-value bycatch (LVB) for non-edible purposes. An unsorted portion of LVB was analyzed at species level to understand the species composition and the juvenile composition in the samples. The main gears used were 4 m beam trawl (BT) and two types of otter trawl, the ‘Grande overture vertical’ (GOV) trawl and ‘Portuguese high headline trawl’ (PHHT), which samples different fishes (in terms of species composition and size distribution). Beam trawl surveys are designed to collect commercial flatfish species (e.g. plaice and sole) and also collect a variety of non-commercial species (e.g. dragonets and lesser-spotted dogfish, poor cod, solenette, pogge,). The otter trawls were better adapted to collect round fishes (e.g. whiting, cod, haddock,) and larger demersal species. The high headline heights of these trawls help for the collection of small pelagic fish (e.g. mackerel and herring). The deep sea shrimp trawlers generally operated between 8°35’ N - 9°55’ N lat and 75°30’ E - 76°15’ E long (300 to 400 m depth), off the southwest coast of India.

The samples were collected from the harbour and brought to the laboratory as fresh as possible to identify the specimens at the species level. The collected samples were kept

in ice and stored in a fish-hold. Qualitative and quantitative analyses of the samples were made in the laboratory. The morphometric analysis is done by using digital vernier calipers. Discarded samples were measured using balances according to the size of the samples. Length and weight data were recorded for all species observed during the surveys, including commercial and non-commercial species. The small-bodied samples were measured more accurately which is collated in Microsoft Excel.

3. Results

The presence of bycatch organisms was found in the Neendakara fishing harbour. The major discarded samples included were crabs, fishes, mollusca and stomatopods. The discarded samples along with their scientific names are given in Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3. The approximate composition of important groups in the bycatch is given in Table 4 (a, b and c). A total of 9 species of crab belonging to 5 families; fishes: 17 species belonging to 16 families; Stomatopoda: 1 species belonging to 1 family; Mollusca: 13 species belonging to 12 families were recorded. *Cynoglossus cynoglossus*, Scienids, Stone crabs, and Button crabs were the predominant types of species recorded as bycatch.

Table 1: Trawl bycatch diversity of crabs in Neendakara Harbour, Kerala, India.

Order	Family	Species
Decapoda	Portunidae	<i>Portunus sanguinolentus</i> (Herbst, 1783) Three-spotted swimming crab
Decapoda	Palicidae	<i>Exopalicus maculatus</i> (Edmondson, 1930) Button Crabs
Decapoda	Portunidae	<i>Charybdis truncata</i> (Fabricius, 1798a) Blunt-toothed crab
Decapoda	Portunidae	<i>Charybdis feriatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758a) Cross crab
Decapoda	Dorippidae	<i>Dorippe astuta</i> Fabricius (Fabricius, 1798b) Spider Crabs
Decapoda	Portunidae	<i>Charybdis lucifera</i> (Fabricius, 1798c) Yellowish brown crab
Decapoda	Menippidae	<i>Menippe mercenaria</i> (Say, 1818) Stone crab
Decapoda	Calappidae	<i>Calappa lophos</i> (Herbst, 1785) Common box crab
Decapoda	Paguroidea	<i>Pagurus bernhardus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758b) Hermit crab

Table 2: Trawl bycatch diversity of fishes in Neendakara Harbour, Kerala, India.

Order	Family	Species
Perciformes	Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus diacanthus</i> (Valenciennes, 1828) Spinycheek grouper
Perciformes	Sciaenidae	<i>Johnius dussumieri</i> (Cuvier, 1830) Scienids
Pleuronectiformes	Cynoglossidae	<i>Cynoglossus cynoglossus</i> (Hamilton, 1822a) Bengal tonguesole

Order	Family	Species
Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	<i>Danio rerio</i> (Hamilton, 1822b) Zebra fish
Perciformes	Leiognathidae	<i>Leiognathus bindus</i> (Valenciennes, 1835) Silverbellies
Perciformes	Polynemidae	<i>Polydactylus sextarius</i> (Bloch and Schneider, 1801a) Blackspot threadfin
Clupeiformes	Clupeidae	<i>Sardinella longiceps</i> (Valenciennes, 1847) Indian oil sardine
Clupeiformes	Engraulidae	<i>Thryssa mystax</i> (Bloch and Schneider, 1801b) The moustached thryssa or Gangetic anchovy
Carangiformes	Carangidae	<i>Megalaspis cordyla</i> (Linnaeus, 1758c) Torpedo scad
Perciformes	Trichiuridae	<i>Lepturacanthus savala</i> (Cuvier, 1829) Ribbon fish
Perciformes	Sillaginidae	<i>Sillago sihama</i> (Forskål, 1775) Silver whiting and sand smelt
Clupeiformes	Engraulidae	<i>Stolephorus indicus</i> (Hasselt, 1823) Anchovies
Carcharhiniformes	Carcharhinidae	<i>Scoliodon laticaudus</i> (Müller and Henle, 1838) Spadenose shark
Perciformes	Ambassidae	<i>Ambassis interrupta</i> (Bleeker, 1853) Long-spined glass perchle
Perciformes	Nemipteridae	<i>Nemipterus japonicus</i> (Bloch, 1791) Japanese threadfin bream
Istiophoriformes	Sphyraenidae	<i>Sphyraena barracuda</i> (Edwards, 1771) The great barracuda
Carangiformes	Carangidae	<i>Carangoides malabaricus</i> (Bloch and Schneider, 1801c) Carangids

Table 3: Trawl bycatch diversity of Stomatopoda and molluscans in Neendakara harbour, Kerala, India.

Order	Family	Species and Common Name
Stomatopoda Molluscans	Squillidae	<i>Oratosquilla nepa</i> https://eprints.cmfri.org.in/784/
Littorinimorpha	Bursidae	<i>Bursa spinosa</i> / <i>Bufonaria echinata</i> (Link, 1807; Schumacher, 1817)
Neogastropoda	Babyloniidae	<i>Babylonia spirata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758d)
Littorinimorpha	Ficidae	<i>Ficus gracillus</i> (Sowerby, 1825) Graceful fig shell
Littorinimorpha	Tonnidae	<i>Tona dolium</i> (Linnaeus, 1758e) Spotted tun
Neogastropoda	Clavatulidae	<i>Sarcula amicta</i> (<i>Turris amicta</i>) (Smith, 1877) Sarcula javana
Neogastropoda	Muricidae	<i>Murex trapa</i> (Röding, 1798) Rare-spined murex
Neogastropoda	Fascioliidae	<i>Fusinus forceps</i> (Perry, 1811)
Neogastropoda	Harpidae	<i>Harpa conoidalis</i> (Lamarck, 1822)
Caenogastropoda	Turritellidae	<i>Turritella duplicata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758f)
Trochida	Turbinidae	<i>Turbo sparverius</i> (Gmelin, 1791) The corded turban
Neogastropoda	Conidae	<i>Conus textile</i> (Linnaeus, 1758g) The textile cone
Arcida	Arcidae	<i>Tegillarca granosa</i> (<i>Anadara granosa</i>) (Linnaeus, 1758h) Blood clam
Neogastropoda	Ancillariidae	<i>Murex echinata</i> (<i>Raphitoma echinata</i>) (Brocchi, 1814)

Table 4a: Important organisms found in the trawl bycatch in Neendakara harbour, Kerala, India.

Species	Total Nos.	Weight (g)	Length (Smallest mm)	Ind. Wt (g)	Biggest (mm)	Ind. Wt (g)
Trawling 22-04-2015 Crabs Males						
<i>Portunus sanguinolentus</i>	2	26.47	62	12.92	64	13.55
<i>Exopalicus maculatus</i>	34	1988.3	14	1.02	28	10.4
<i>Charybdis. truncata</i>	4	21.83	26	3.97	35	5.86
Trawling 22-04-2015 Crabs Females						
<i>Charybdis feriatius</i>	2	57.12	60	14	72	43.12
<i>Exopalicus maculatus</i>	34	1063.6	12	2.6	22	5.71
<i>Charybdis. truncata</i>	11	39.81	26	3.35	37	3.88
<i>Dorippe astuta Fabricus</i>	4	21.55	20	3.92	28	9.29
Trawling 23-04-2015 Crabs Males						
<i>Portunus sanguinolentus</i>	2	26	64	13.15	67	12.85
<i>Exopalicus maculatus</i>	10	43.83	16	2.33	27	8.49
<i>Charybdis. truncata</i>	2	8.38	30	3.85	30	4.53
<i>Dorippe astuta Fabricus</i>	7	29.9	17	1.92	28	5.43
<i>Charybdis. truncata</i>	4	14.33	27	3.39	30	4.33
<i>Charybdis. lucifera</i>	3	15.76	25	2.06	45	9.3
<i>Exopalicus maculatus</i>	16	72.27	15	0.9	27	9.73
Trawling 23-04-2015 Crabs Females						
<i>Charybdis lucifera</i>	2	13.7	35	4.4	45	9.3
<i>Exopalicus maculatus</i>	21	60.32	15	1.43	22	4.7
<i>Charybdis. truncata</i>	2	5.95	27	3.39	28	2.56
<i>Exopalicus maculatus</i>	12	43.05	12	1.25	22	4.35
<i>Dorippe astuta Fabricus</i>	2	18.6	28	9.3	29	9.3
<i>Menippe mercenaria</i>	54	159.3	12	1.8	16	27
<i>Menippe mercenaria</i>	32	176.1	13	2.2	24	12.29
<i>Calappa lophos</i>	2	10	28.09	4.8	29.89	5.2

Table 4b: Important organisms found in the trawl bycatch in Neendakara harbour, Kerala, India.

Species	Total Nos.	Weight (g)	Length (Smallest mm)	Ind. Wt (g)	Biggest (mm)	Ind. Wt (g)
<i>Epinephelus diacanthus</i>	8	100.6	95	12.27	138	4.78
<i>Johnius dussumieri</i>	25	313.63	45	25.12	140	26.89
<i>Cynoglossus cynoglossus</i>	33	339.68	62	1.78	272	11.75
<i>Danio rerio</i>	5	33.1	75	2.77	150	15.0
<i>Leiognathus bindus</i>	1	12.39	98	12.40	96	13.29
<i>Polydactylus sextarius</i>	1	27.57	133	27.57	133	27.57
<i>Sardinella longiceps</i>	2	127.7	180	66.2	192	61.5
<i>Thryssa mystax</i>	3	43.1	107	14	110	14.4
<i>Megalaspis cordyla</i>	2	14.4	90	6.4	93	75
<i>Lepturacanthus savala</i>	2	26.3	267	10.5	295	15.8
<i>Sillago sihama</i>	2	18	98	7.6	110	10.4
<i>Stolephorus indicus</i>	2	5.9	75	2.9	83	3
<i>Scoliodon laticaudus</i>	4	35.9	105	4.1	245	20.6
<i>Ambassis interrupta</i>	30	112.1	65	2.6	85	5
<i>Nemipterus japonicus</i>	8	1911.16	250	166.6	353	373.16
<i>Sphyraena barracuda</i>	2	11.6	106	6.1	11	5.5
<i>Carangoides malabaricus</i>	11	116.4	93	6.9	112	14

Table 4c: Important organisms found in the trawl bycatch in Neendakara harbour, Kerala, India.

Species	Total Nos.	Weight (g)	Length (Smallest mm)	Ind. Wt (g)	Biggest (mm)	Ind. Wt (g)
Stomatopodes Male						
<i>Oratosquilla nepa</i>	51	186.4	25	5.2	98	5.8
Molluscs						
<i>Bursa spinosa (Bufonaria echinata)</i> with hermit crab	17	230.78	22.83	3.15	64.55	21.47
<i>Babylonia spirata</i> with empty shell	2	16.82	30	4.77	39.47	12.05
<i>Babylonia</i> with hermit crab	3	68.58	48.88	25.88	54.47	19.36
<i>Bursa spinosa (Bufonaria echinata)</i> without animal	3	46.01	46.98	11.46	68.67	23.4
<i>Ficus gracillus</i> (Graceful fig shell)	6	69	37	6.8	60	69.2
<i>Tona dolium</i>	2	44.1	27	36	67	40.5
<i>Sarca amicta</i>	62	132.9	26	0.7	62	5.1
<i>Murex trapa</i>	10	99.73	23	0.67	80	18.92
<i>Fusinus forceps</i>	4	19.43	25	0.86	68	10.15
<i>Turritella duplicata</i>	12	96.54	35	2.02	80	12.62
<i>Turbo sparverius</i>	9	41.3	21	1.6	33	8.9
<i>Conus textile</i>	2	16.5	33.04	7.4	37.07	9.1
<i>Anadar ragranosa</i>	5	9.2	14.7	1.6	16.84	1.8
<i>Murex echinata</i>	6	55.5	40.28	2.8	75.62	13.1

3.1. Composition of Discards

The total length of the collected animals ranged from 12 to 180mm and the weight from 1.02 g to 372.16g. On average, a long-trip boat brings 1 tonne of fishes as bycatch per trip, while for a daily trip, it is 100-500 kg. The samples from long-trip boats were limited to 25 per cent of the total since most of the long-trip bycatch was in putrid condition by the time it landed. Morphometric study is a powerful tool for characterizing strains of the same species, which involves

detection of variation of shape, independent of size. Similarly, a mathematical representation of the length-weight relationship derived from the study of different sexes and sizes from a particular area is a very useful tool for the study of fisheries assessment, biology, ecology, physiology, population dynamics, and general conditions of the studied population. It is also plays an important role in population assessment (Ricker, 1968).

Wade et al. (2021) reported that bycatch might threaten the marine environment due to the decrease in the population

of different species. This study is an attempt to understand the problems related to bycatch organisms. During the study, a total of 597 bycatch organisms were encountered at the sampling station (A total of 9 species of crab belonging to 5 families; fishes: 17 species belonging to 16 families; Stomatopoda: 1 species belonging to 1 family; Mollusca: 14 species belonging to 13 families). This is in conformity with the result obtained by previous research conducted by Madhu et al. (2017), the presence of bycatch organisms was identified in the trawl catch. Gibinkumar et al. (2012) also reported 281 species including juveniles of commercially important shellfishes and fishes from the shrimp trawl bycatch along the Cochin region.

In our study, 14 species of molluscans were identified. Species like *Bursa spinosa* (*Bufo naria echinata*), *Babylonia spirata*, *Murex trapa*, *Fusinus forceps*, *Turitella duplicate* etc. were the most predominant molluscans recorded in this study. In the marine environment, mollusca is a phylum known for ecosystem engineering. These species may also be utilized as indicators of environmental health, for medical, commercial, nutritional purposes etc. Declining in the population of molluscan species due to bycatch eventually affects the balance of the marine environment. Some of the earlier works also reported the presence of huge amounts of molluscan species as bycatch. Sirajudheen and Biju Kumar (2014), conducted a taxonomic survey to understand the diversity of ornamental fishes in the trawl bycatch of the Neendakara fishing harbour and documented the presence of 138 species belonging to 14 orders 67 families and 108 genera. Similarly, Souji and Tresa (2015) conducted a study in the Neendakara harbour. The study revealed that molluscan species were the dominant species that landed by-catch during the study period. Appukuttan (2008) reported a total of 3271 species of molluscs belonging to 220 families and 591 genera, of which 1900 are gastropods, 1100 bivalves, 210 cephalopods, 41 polyplacophorans and 20 scaphopods from India. Deepthi (2009) conducted a study and reported 128 species of Mollusca. *Portunus Sanguinolentus*, *Exopalicus maculatus*, *Dorippe astuta Fabricus*, and *Calappa lophos* etc. were the predominant types of crabs. *Epinephelus diacanthus*, *Johnius dussumieri*, *Cynoglossus cynoglossus*, and *Sardinella longiceps* etc. were the predominant types of fish species. Crab and fish species are commercially important groups widely used for nutrient resources and other commercial purposes. Kurup et al. (2003) also conducted a similar study and re-

ported 103 species of fin fishes, 65 gastropods, 12 bivalves, 8 shrimps, 2 stomatopods, and 12 crabs, 5 cephalopods, 3 echinoderms, 4 jelly fishes as discards by bottom trawlers in Kerala coast. Bycatch organisms were also recorded in a study conducted by Karan et al. (2023). Gradually there is a chance of a decline in the population of organisms and thus it will directly or indirectly affect the balance of nature. Davies et al. (2009) reported that bycatch constitutes approximately 40.4% of the estimated annual global marine catch of 95 million tonnes. Juvenile organisms were also encountered at the sampling stations. This may affect the population of marine organisms (Lewison et al., 2004) suggested that bycatch-related mortality is also among the main causes of declines in threatened marine megafauna including sea turtles, cetaceans, and sea birds. Foster and Vincent (2010) also reported that resilient species can be threatened as bycatch, like juvenile fish constitute a major proportion of the catch in tropical shrimp trawlers. Thus our results are following the above-said reports.

Bycatch is also a threat to livelihoods and food security in general. Fish is one of the healthiest foods. In Kerala, the level of fish consumption is four times the national average and there exists a significant demand for high-value fish and fish products. Considering the annual per capita fish consumption has increased from 15 kg in the 1970s to about 23 kg in 2011 (Shyam et al., 2020). In our study 18 fish species were encountered as bycatch organisms. It might lead to a decrease in the fish sources thus affecting the local food consumption. Lobo et al. (2004) reported that the small-scale fisheries sector contributes food to local markets, thus the bycatch might lead to the depletion of this food source for local consumption. Thus our observations corroborate the findings made by these researchers.

4. Discussion

In our study, we could understand that the commercialization of bycatch is another major problem. In countries like India, where the per capita protein availability is below the recommended level, the proper utilization of bycatch from trawlers is important. Mince extracted from fishes like small sciaenids, engraulids, carangids, etc. can be used for making products like fish balls, crackers and burgers (Yu and Siah, 1996). Lobo et al. (2010) and Lobo (2012) reported that the commercialization of bycatch may help

sustain the profits of a fishery that can no longer survive solely on the revenue from traditionally targeted stocks. Lobo et al. (2004) reported that in India, this trend can be attributed to several causes. These include Declining profits from target catch, New markets for bycatch species or products, and Fishmeal as feed in the poultry and aquaculture industries. Even while this might seem positive, the fisheries will probably be overfished and the bycatch stocks will also be overfished. In addition to being a relevant ecological threat, this report also indicated that it is a livelihood and social justice issue. The exploitation of the higher-value (previously targeted but now depleted) species can go on, driving them to extinction, mainly to the income from low-value bycatch. This further facilitates the degradation of marine benthic habitats. Our observations are also following the above-said report.

The relationship between length and weight of organisms was also noted in our study. Length-weight relationships (LWRs) and relative condition factors are of great importance in fishery assessment studies. It provides pieces of information about the growth of the fish, its general well-being, and fitness in a marine habitat (Jisr et al., 2018). The relationship between length and weight is required for setting up a yield equation and sometimes it may be useful as a character to differentiate “small taxonomic units”. The length-weight relationship also provides means for finding out the “condition factor” and the seasonal changes in the condition factor are useful to determine the biological changes in the fish.

5. Conclusion

In today’s world, one of the conservation issues facing fisheries is “bycatch”, for which there are currently no definitive solutions. Fisheries are a fast growing economic sector all around the world. It provides protein-rich food and is a good source of employing millions of people. Trawling and dredging are the two types of modern fishing methods used worldwide. These modern fishing techniques, particularly some of them are highly harmful to the marine ecosystem. Trawling is towing a net behind a boat at various depths, directly affects the sea bottom. Due to trawling the sea bottom is disturbed and churned up by scraping, physical destruction of bedforms, sediment re-suspension and removal or scattering of non-target benthos. The cumulative effect and intensity of trawling may result in long-term changes in

benthic communities. Assessment of bycatch and discards will be further helpful in framing remedies for a sustainable fishery. Thus we can develop management policies to conserve the marine ecosystem and biodiversity.

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Author Contributions

Vincent D. K. contributed considerably during the collection, analysis and interpretation of data, analysis of the results and write-up of the manuscript. Manuscript preparation was performed by Soumya. K. and Mohamed Hatha A. A. have made substantial contributions to the design and acquisition of data, analysis and interpretation of results and has been involved in revising the manuscript and has given final approval of the version to be published. The authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing interests.

Data Availability Statement

On an adequate request, the corresponding author will provide the data used in this work.

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